

INCREASING EFFICIENCY AND STRENGTHENING CONSUMER PROTECTION IN THE OLIGOPOLISTIC MOBILE TELEPHONY MARKET. THE ECONOMIC AND REGULATORY MODEL IN ALBANIA

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ABSTRACT: *The evolution of the mobile telephony market in Albania shows a transition from an initial monopoly, towards a phase of dynamic competition, and then towards a concentrated oligopoly, where consumer benefits have diminished despite technological development. Market practice shows elements of open coordination between the two operators, reducing the positive effects of competition on price and service quality, despite the formal liberalization of the market and the harmonization of the legal framework with European Union standards. The study aims to assess which economic and regulatory model appears most suitable for improving the functioning of the Albanian mobile telephony market, based on the theory of oligopoly (Cournot and Bertrand models). The methodology includes a combined approach of reviewing theoretical and institutional literature, analysis of official reports of AKEP and the Competition Authority and studies by foreign authors on this problem. The expected results show that the addition of new operators to the market does not necessarily guarantee a sustainable reduction in prices, due to structural barriers, high entry costs and customer loyalty to existing operators. In this context, a hybrid approach, which combines elements of Bertrand-type competition with active regulatory intervention, tariff transparency and the promotion of alternative models of competition, such as virtual mobile network operators (MVNOs) and infrastructure sharing, turns out to be more effective. The study also argues that corporate social responsibility (CSR) can play a complementary role in mitigating the social effects of oligopoly, contributing to consumer protection, increasing public trust and improving market ethics. In conclusion, the study suggests that resolving the current situation in the Albanian mobile telephony market requires a combination of competitive policies, economic regulation and social engagement of operators, rather than simply increasing the number of operators in the market.*

KEYWORDS: *Oligopoly market, mobile telephony, economic regulation, consumer protection, market efficiency, competition policies*

1. Introduction

The telecommunications sector has grown tremendously since the beginning of the 21st century, both in developed and developing countries. The rapid growth in the telecommunications sector is attributed to sector reforms and mainly market liberalization. The liberalization of telecommunications markets began around the 1980s and 1990s in most developed and developing countries. Due to technological advances, the telecommunications sector plays an important and influential role in other sectors such as education, trade, agriculture and health. The connection between the telecommunications sector and other sectors explains the vitality of the former and its potential to drive economic growth in the modern world, thus playing a crucial role in achieving sustainable development objectives. The same growth trend has been observed in the telecommunications sector in Albania. The mobile telephony market in Albania has undergone a rapid transformation process since the 1990s, moving from a monopolistic structure towards a concentrated oligopolistic market. In the early stages of liberalization, the entry of new operators and technological development created conditions for increased competition, lower prices and wider consumer access to mobile services. However,

subsequent processes of market consolidation, the reduction of the number of operators and the increase of structural barriers have led to a gradual weakening of competitive intensity. In economic terms, the current oligopolistic structure is characterized by limited price competition, tariff stabilization and package differentiation that often makes real comparison difficult for consumers. The behavior of operators is closer to theoretical models of Cournot-type oligopoly (Cournot, A. A. 1838) and open coordination, than to pure Bertrand-type competition (Bertrand, J. 1883). As a result, the benefits usually expected from market liberalization are not fully reflected in consumer welfare. Consumer protection is becoming a common topic of discussion among policymakers, researchers and other stakeholders around the world. International organizations such as the United Nations (UN), the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the European Union (EU) have directives, manuals or guidelines on consumer protection (UNCTAD, 2016). Consumer protection in telecommunications markets has been adopted mainly to strike the right balance between consumers and service providers, first by protecting consumers from unfair business practices, second by providing information and education to consumers and third by assisting the aggrieved consumer in the process of complaining and seeking redress. In addition to the benefits of consumer welfare, consumer protection is expected to compel suppliers or service providers to provide a high quality of services and refrain from unfair business practices, thereby increasing efficiency in the market.

From a legal and regulatory point of view, Albania has a normative framework harmonized with the European Union legislation in the field of competition and consumer protection. However, the main challenge remains the effective implementation of this framework in practice. The role of regulatory and supervisory institutions has increased in recent years, but interventions are often reactive rather than preventive, allowing the preservation of oligopolistic structures in the market.

In the social dimension, the effect of oligopoly is reflected in the perception of consumers of a lack of real choice, limited tariff transparency and difficulties in changing operator. Forced loyalty to existing operators, combined with the complexity of offers, reduces the bargaining power of consumers and increases sensitivity to practices that are not fully transparent.

The study emphasizes that the addition of new operators to the market, as the only solution, does not necessarily guarantee increased competition and sustainable price reductions. On the contrary, an integrated approach is required, which combines active competition policies, consumer-oriented economic regulation and alternative competition instruments, such as virtual network operators (MVNO), infrastructure unbundling and strengthening tariff transparency.

In this context, corporate social responsibility (CSR) appears as an important complementary element, contributing to increasing market ethics, protecting vulnerable groups and building public trust. Integrating CSR with regulatory policies can help mitigate the social effects of oligopoly and improve market sustainability in the long term.

In conclusion, the topic argues that solving the problems of the Albanian mobile telephony market requires a multidimensional approach, where the economy, law and social dimensions are treated in an interconnected manner, moving from a purely structural logic towards a functional model of sustainable competition.

2. Literature review

The economic theory of oligopoly, according to the classical literature, focuses on the strategic behavior of firms and the effects on prices, production and consumer welfare. Cournot (1838) analyzes competition through quantities, showing that in markets with few

firms prices tend to be higher than in perfect competition. Bertrand (1883) demonstrates that competition through prices can theoretically lead to lower prices, but only if the products are homogeneous and there are no entry barriers. Contemporary studies (Tirole, 1988; Vives, 1999) emphasize that in sectors such as telecommunications, oligopoly is a “natural” structure due to high fixed costs, the need for licensed frequency spectrum, and network effects. Oligopoly and telecommunications market performance has been addressed by authors such as Armstrong & Sappington (2007) and Laffont&Tirole (2000), who analyze how oligopolies in Telecoms affect price levels, service quality, and technological innovation. The main findings show that the addition of operators does not automatically guarantee price reductions if consumers are inelastic and brand loyal.

The addition of operators affects the reduction of prices only if it is accompanied by structural policies such as the entry of MVNOs (Mobile Virtual Network Operators) that use the existing infrastructure, have lower costs, offer more aggressive prices. In many EU countries, MVNOs have reduced tariffs, increased competitive pressure. Strong regulation of access to infrastructure, functional separation of networks, equal access to the frequency spectrum, wholesale controlled tariffs. Mandatory price transparency consisting of a ban on hidden fees, standardization of packages, real comparability for the consumer. This activates competition on the demand side. Strengthening the Competition Authority, which deals with monitoring and coordinating price understanding, real penalties for anti-competitive behavior, proactive interventions, not just reactive ones.

According to scholars in the field, liberalization involves improving consumer choice, sovereignty, and bargaining power, which in turn should lead to higher perceived consumer satisfaction (Hulsink, 2012). However, even with the presence of liberalized markets, consumer satisfaction in the telecommunications sector is still low, both in developing and developed countries (Lopez, R., Amaral, T., Garín-Muñoz, T., &Gijón, C. 2015). Furthermore, it is now clear that competitive markets alone do not necessarily translate into better services, as research shows that even in competitive markets, there may be low-quality service providers. This is because, as competition becomes fierce and profit margins erode, service providers have little incentive to increase their investments in providing better quality services if such decisions do not lead to comparable financial returns. As a result, consumers are more likely to be exploited in telecommunications markets, which has raised the need for consumer protection to ensure that consumers receive value for money and have bargaining power. In addition to contributing to the growth of the telecommunications sector, liberalization was expected to improve consumer sovereignty by creating choice in markets through competition, thus leading to higher consumer satisfaction (Jordana& Levi-Faur, 2004). The situation is particularly worse in developing countries, where service quality is consistently poor (Appiah, 2011; Fripp, 2012; Mumo, 2016; TCRA, 2015). This persistence of poor service quality and low consumer satisfaction in telecommunications markets suggests that liberalization alone does not guarantee consumer sovereignty (Lopez, et al. 2015; Smith, 2000). Antitrust and consumer protection laws share a common goal of facilitating the exercise of effective consumer choice (Cherry 2010).

According to OECD (2018) and European Commission (2020), the main problems for consumers in oligopolistic markets are hidden prices, complex contracts, information asymmetry, high switching costs. Researcher Stiglitz (2000) emphasizes that markets with incomplete information require regulatory intervention to protect consumers and increase efficiency. The role of regulation and supervisory authorities from studies by ITU, World Bank and European Regulators Group (BEREC) show that the most successful models combine ex ante wholesale price regulation, tariff transparency, strengthening consumer rights, and monitoring anti-competitive behavior. Examples from Croatia, Romania and the

Baltic countries show that improving market functioning has come more from smart regulation, not from the addition of operators. According to the literature, authors such as Porter & Kramer (2011) link corporate social responsibility in telecommunications CSR with the creation of shared value, arguing that companies in concentrated markets have increased responsibility towards society. In the telecommunications sector, CSR is associated with equal access to services, fair prices, digital education, and transparency towards consumers. Empirical studies (The evolution of the Albanian market is reflected in the studies of AKEP, INSTAT and the reports of the European Commission for Albania which show that the Albanian market has gone from monopoly to competition and then to oligopoly where the consolidation of operators has increased market concentration, prices for the consumer remain relatively high compared to average income. The mobile telephony market in Albania is today a concentrated oligopolistic market, where a few main operators dominate the vast majority of the market. Institutional studies and reports confirm that this structure has brought low risk of competition in prices and offers for consumers. AKEP underlines that the current duopoly may increase prices and limit consumer benefits if the regulatory role is not strengthened with prior intervention. Market analyses show that after the merger of operators, the mobile communications market in Albania is mainly owned by two companies, and this situation may create conditions for coordinated behavior between them on prices and package structures. Comparative reports show that mobile services in Albania cost more than the European Union average, a possible indicator of the lack of effective competition in the market. Empirical evidence for oligopolistic behavior and prices is clearly seen in studies showing that, in practice, the behavior of mobile operators in Albania may have elements of price and package coordination, limiting consumer choice and increasing costs towards profitability. The Competition Authority has initiated in-depth investigations into the main operators, examining practices that may limit competition in the retail market for mobile services and possible anti-competitive practices. Social and pricing analysis also shows that when one operator increases the prices of prepaid packages, the other tends to follow this increase in a short period, which suggests symmetrical and coordinated behavior of the main market operators. The role of the regulator and the competition policies of the Albanian supervisory authorities, such as AKEP and the Competition Authority, have raised ongoing concerns about the risks of oligopolistic structures and the need for regulatory response. AKEP has highlighted the need for legal changes that give more power to ex-ante regulatory intervention, in order to prevent concerted practices that harm competition and consumers. The Competition Authority also recommends that the retail market for mobile services be subject to direct regulation by AKEP, creating opportunities for policies that promote effective competition and consumer protection. Finally, the Assembly's requirements for monitoring specific markets also include the mobile sector, placing increased emphasis on consumer protection and competition law enforcement. Previous research on efficiency and competitive barriers as well as international theoretical and empirical studies on oligopolistic markets, including models of price and quantity competition, suggest that markets with few players tend to produce higher prices and limited competition if regulation is inadequate (Cournot, Bertrand). These findings are supported by the microeconomics and industrial organization literature, which emphasizes the importance of competition policies and regulatory intervention to prevent anticompetitive behavior and protect consumers. Jamali & Mirshak, (2007) show that CSR can serve as a self-regulatory mechanism in oligopolistic markets.

The history of the mobile telephony market in Albania after the 1990s begins with the initial liberalization phase (1995–2003) where a monopolistic market dominates, i.e. embryonic competition. After the fall of the socialist system, the telecommunications sector in Albania started from a state-owned monopolistic structure, with limited services and

backward technology. The introduction of mobile telephony in the mid-1990s marked the entry of the first mobile operator, a gradual increase in territorial coverage, high prices and limited access, so we are dealing with mobile telephony as an “elite” service. In this phase, the market is characterized by a lack of real competition, an orientation towards network expansion, not towards the consumer, and low elasticity of demand due to high prices. The competitive expansion phase (2004–2012) which moves from duopoly to relative competition with the entry of new operators and the improvement of the regulatory framework, the market moved towards an oligopolistic structure with functional competition, accompanied by the rapid increase in cellular penetration with progressive price reductions, more diverse tariff offers, strong investments in infrastructure. (2G–3G). In this phase: competition was more aggressive, the consumer benefited from promotional offers, loyalty to the operator was still weak, the market was closer to the Bertrand model with differentiation. This period is considered the most dynamic phase of competition in the Albanian market. The consolidation phase (2013–2018) is characterized by a reduction in operators, increased concentration, where after 2013, the market began to experience the exit of several operators, mergers and acquisitions, increased operating costs, market saturation, i.e. a penetration of over 100%. As a result, this phase had several main consequences such as: a decrease in competitive intensity, stabilization of prices at relatively high levels, increased complexity of packages, strengthening of barriers to switching operators. The market begins to exhibit elements of a functional duopoly, with indirectly coordinated behavior. The concentrated oligopolistic phase (2019 to date) where we are dealing with limited structural competition. In recent years, the mobile telephony market in Albania has been characterized by high market concentration, dominance of a few major operators, competition mainly in marketing, not in real prices, increased concerns for consumers (hidden fees, transparency). This phase is characterized by these features: behavior similar to the Cournot model (Cournot, A. A. (1838), where quantity control in offers dominates, high consumer loyalty, a more active role of the regulator and the Competition Authority, pressure from the EU to strengthen consumer protection. If we were to compare the situation before and after oligopolistic consolidation, we would identify **6 variables** that make it possible for us to have a comparative situation, respectively according to the following table:

	Element	Before oligopoly (2004–2012)	After oligopoly (2019 to date)
1	Number of operators	Higher	Reduced
2	Competitive intensity	Strong	Limited
3	Prices	Downward trend	Stabilization, relative increase
4	Consumer choice	Wide	Limited
5	Transparency	Average	Problematic
6	Role of the regulator	Supervisory	Active interventionist

In conclusion, we emphasize that the evolution of the mobile telephony market in Albania shows a transition from an initial monopoly, towards a phase of dynamic competition, and then towards a concentrated oligopoly, where consumer benefits have diminished despite technological development. The history highlights the need for more active competition policies, consumer-focused regulation and alternative competition models (MVNO, infrastructure sharing, CSR). A realistic and effective solution would be

the entry of MVNOs (Dewenter, R., & Haucap, J. 2005). (Kim, J., & Seol, S. 2007) emphasize that “strong regulation of infrastructure access would have effects on prices, i.e. real reductions”. Price transparency is essentially competitive pressure (Marcus, J. S. 2010). Consumer education directly affects the strengthening of demand. Active antitrust investigations by hindering cooperation between operators. While the addition of operators alone would have a limited effect on reducing real prices. In the conditions of an oligopolistic market like Albania's, effective competition requires institutional intervention, price transparency, and mechanisms that empower the consumer.

In conclusion, the addition of companies to the mobile telephony market does not guarantee price reductions unless accompanied by structural regulatory reforms. The analysis of the evolution of the Albanian mobile telephony market is based on official reports of AKEP and the Competition Authority, combined with classical and modern literature on oligopolies and regulated competition. The literature review reveals a clear consensus that oligopolistic structures in mobile markets require strong competition policies and proactive regulatory interventions to improve commercial efficiency and protect consumers from harmful competitive practices.

3. Methodology

Research methodology involves a number of activities that need to be carried out. According to Howell, K. E. (2013), methodology describes “the overall research strategy that determines how the research is carried out”. For this reason, one of the first steps in planning a research process is a literature review, which involves searching all sources of information to track the latest knowledge, assessing its relevance to our topic, quality, contradictions and gaps. This study is based on the qualitative analysis of secondary data, including official institutional reports, legal documents and academic literature. Secondary research is a collection of work that has been done and published by several researchers in this field, which is available for others to use in their study. Secondary data sources can be collected from various sources such as books, journals, official bulletins etc. This paper uses a qualitative analytical approach, combined with comparative elements, to analyze the oligopolistic structure in the mobile telephony market in Albania and to present a more appropriate economic and regulatory model for improving the functioning of the Albanian mobile telephony market. The study is mainly based on: Systematic review of international academic literature on oligopoly theory, competition in telecommunications and consumer protection; Analysis of official documents and institutional reports of national authorities (AKEP, Competition Authority, Supreme State Audit Office, INSTAT); Analysis of the Albanian legal and regulatory framework, in relation to European Union standards and practices. To connect the theory to the Albanian reality, the study uses comparative analysis with small European countries with similar market structures, identifying successful regulatory practices applicable in Albania. The data are analyzed through thematic analysis, categorizing the findings according to the two main dimensions of the study: analyzing the oligopolistic structure and the economic and regulatory model. This approach allows an integrated assessment of the impact of oligopolistic structure on competition, price transparency and consumer welfare. The methodological advantages are related to adapting to the lack of public microeconomic data, ensuring coherence between theory and practice, and being suitable for policy and regulatory analysis. In the first phase of the study, a systematic literature review was carried out, which includes: classical and contemporary literature on oligopoly theory (Cournot, Bertrand, Tirole), studies on telecommunications markets and economic regulation, reports of international organizations (OECD, ITU, World Bank, European Commission) and the Albanian legal framework and AKEP reports. The legal analysis was carried out through a review of the Albanian regulatory framework

for competition and electronic communications, including Law no. 9121/2003 "On the Protection of Competition", Law no. 9918/2008 "On electronic communications", as well as the relevant sub-legal acts and institutional practices of the Competition Authority and AKEP. To assess the social dimension and the impact on the consumer, reports on consumer protection, studies on information asymmetry and consumer behavior, as well as official documents on price transparency and standard contracts in the telecommunications sector were used. (OECD, 2018; European Consumer Organization, 2021). The analysis is based on the theoretical literature on oligopoly, national and European institutional reports, as well as empirical data on the Albanian mobile telephony market. The aim of this phase was to identify relevant theoretical models and highlight regulatory best practices. The study uses secondary data, which may limit the depth of the review and the reliability of the data. Secondary data may be incomplete, include outdated data, or be influenced by researcher biases, which affect the reliability of the results. This study attempts to provide a new understanding of how oligopoly affects the mobile phone market. By analyzing the consequences of market control and competition, actors will be able to adapt to existing trends and improve the situation. The results confirm that trends require strategic diversification and innovation, as well as compliance with regulations, thus fostering a more competitive environment.

4. Analysis of results

Data from reports by AKEP, the European Commission and international organizations regarding market structure and concentration show that the Albanian mobile telephony market has moved from a structure with several operators to a concentrated oligopolistic structure, practically a duopoly. This market is characterized by a limited number of active operators, a high level of market share concentration and high entry barriers (licenses, spectrum, infrastructure investments). This structure creates a risk of tacit price coordination, tariff rigidity, lack of strong competitive pressure. From the perspective of oligopoly theory, the situation approaches the Cournot model with product differentiation, where competition is limited and prices tend to remain above the optimal level for the consumer. The analysis of prices and accessibility according to international comparative data results in that nominal prices are not necessarily the highest in the region, but the price/income ratio is relatively unfavorable for the Albanian consumer and the packages are complex and often include promotional elements that make real comparison difficult. This analysis suggests limited tariff transparency, incomplete information for the consumer and hidden or distributed costs in the package structure. From an economic point of view, this is typical of markets with information asymmetry, where operators have an information advantage towards consumers. The data show that in terms of competitive behavior and innovation, investments in 4G/5G networks have taken place, but real differentiation of services remains limited and competition focuses more on packages than on structural innovation. In oligopolistic markets, firms often avoid aggressive price competition to maintain margins, focusing on branding, short-term promotional offers and customer segmentation. This brings a stable but not optimal balance for consumer welfare. The analysis of the legal framework and official reports shows that there is a formal legal framework for consumer protection, but implementation and monitoring remain a challenge and consumer complaints do not necessarily represent the real level of dissatisfaction. The main problems relate to partial contractual transparency, changes in tariff conditions, complexity of terms of use. From a regulatory perspective, the market needs more active ex ante supervision, control of tariff practices and strengthening the role of the authority competition. So, the market functions, but does not reach the optimal level of dynamic efficiency and full consumer protection.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

1. The Albanian mobile telephony market is characterized by an oligopolistic structure with a high level of concentration.
2. Competition is more strategic than aggressive in terms of prices.
3. Tariff transparency and information asymmetry constitute the main problem for the consumer.
4. The legal framework exists, but requires strengthening in terms of practical implementation.
5. Market efficiency is relative and conditioned by regulatory intervention.
6. Strengthening competition through wholesale market regulation
7. Reducing administrative barriers to potential entry
8. Monitoring market concentration
9. Stronger regulation of tariff transparency
10. Standardization of package presentation
11. Prior control of contractual changes
12. Strengthening cooperation between AKEP and the Competition Authority
13. Digital education on comparing offers
14. Public price comparison platform
15. Increasing accessibility of complaint mechanisms
16. Integration of CSR practices by operators
17. The study shows that the main problem is not simply the number of operators, but the quality of regulation and market transparency.
18. An integrated economic and regulatory approach, oriented towards the consumer, is essential for increasing the efficiency of the oligopolistic mobile telephony market in Albania.

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